

Gas atomization of γ -TiAl alloy powder for additive manufacturing

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Abstract

The aim of the present work is, first, to optimize gas atomization of a γ -TiAl alloy at the laboratory scale (atomized mass < 150 g) and, second, to investigate the microstructure of the produced powders. Gas atomization variables, such as the gas pressure and the melt temperature, are adjusted to produce the highest yield of particles with sizes smaller than 150 μm . The morphology and microstructure of these powders is characterized by scanning and electron microscopy, as well as by electron backscatter diffraction. The fine particles of interest are found to be single α_2 polycrystals with spherical shape and negligible porosity. Overall, these particles meet the morphological requirements of raw powders for additive manufacturing powder based methods, provided the small loss of Al that takes place during melting is compensated by increasing the amount of this component in the starting alloy.

Keywords: Gas atomization, TiAl, microstructure, additive manufacturing, powder.

1. Introduction

1 Additive manufacturing (AM)^[1-3] technologies allow the fabrication of parts with complex
2 geometries on a layer-by-layer basis. More specifically, in powder bed techniques, successive layers
3 of metallic powders are spread along the building platform using a rake, and then an automatically
4 controlled heat source is utilized to melt and weld the areas of interest. The heat source can either
5 be a laser beam, as in the case of "Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF)" or an electron beam (electron
6 beam melting, EBM). AM technologies are envisioned as key enablers of the next revolution in
7 industrial technologies, as they facilitate on-site manufacturing, part customization, and
8 digitalization of production processes.

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Research is under way to understand what powder characteristics influence powder flowability, thus ensuring a homogeneous powder spreading capability, and reducing the presence of defects in the final part.^[4] Although the preparation of standards is still ongoing, it is often stated that the ideal raw powder must be constituted by a fine dispersion of spherical particles, with sizes ranging from 10 to 50 μm in LPBF and from 50 to 150 μm in EBM. Flowability is also known to be limited by humidity, which leads to particle agglomeration, or by the presence of oxides in the particle surfaces.^[5]

Gas atomization^[6] is currently the powder processing method of choice for the production of AM powders. Although ten times more costly than water atomization, it yields much better particle sphericity, a critical contributor to flowability. During gas atomization an initial alloy is melted in a crucible and, then, a stream of the liquid metal is poured and later pulverized by a jet of pressurized gas. Metal droplets finally solidify during their flight towards a powder collector. Process parameters such as the gas pressure and purity, the melt temperature and flow, as well as the nozzle type, among others, are known to influence the quality and size of the powders^[7,8]. Gas atomization involves very rapid cooling rates, ranging from 10^4 to 10^6 degrees per second depending of particle size, and thus powder microstructures are usually metastable. Little is still known about the

1 influence of the microstructure of the powder and, in particular, of the phase distribution, both at the
2 surface and interior of particles, on AM part printability.

3 Due to the small number of alloys that are suitable for AM processing^[1,2], the design of new
4 compositions that can lead to adequate AM raw powders is currently deemed urgent. Powder design
5 requires laboratory scale atomization of small batches, amounting approximately to less than two
6 hundred grams, which can be easily handled, stored, dispatched, and discarded, if necessary.
7 Although with the surge of AM an increasing number of laboratories are acquiring and utilizing
8 such laboratory scale atomizers, to date most of the data available on the influence of atomization
9 parameters on the powder microstructure was produced using standard, larger scale systems, which
10 are utilized for traditional powder metallurgy processing.^[6]

11 Gamma titanium aluminides are structural intermetallics with a singular combination of low
12 densities (3.9-4.2 g/cm³) and excellent mechanical properties at high temperature.^[9,10] Therefore,
13 they have long been targeted by aerospace industries aiming to replace the heavier Ni-base
14 superalloys currently used to build lighter and stronger engine components such as, for example,
15 low pressure turbine (LPT) blades.^[11,12] Extensive research efforts during the past two decades^[13-20]
16 have resulted in the development of a wide variety of γ -TiAl alloys with balanced properties such as
17 room temperature elongation-to-failure, fracture toughness, high-temperature strength, creep
18 resistance and oxidation behavior. Moreover, some of these alloys have already found commercial
19 uses.^[21,22]

20 Titanium aluminides have been processed using both **LPBF** and EBM methods, with
21 different degrees of success.^[23-25] Initially the slower cooling rates involved in EBM, working in
22 vacuum and with a preheated powder, were found to lead to more robust components, endowed
23 with higher densities. In contrast, **LPBF** led to parts with a high content of pores and a large density
24 of cracks.^[23] However, recent studies are showing promising results in **LPBF**ed γ -TiAl specimens
25 with high Nb content.^[26,27] Further work is still needed to optimize processing parameters of

1 different γ -TiAl alloys. This will require an important initial effort in the fabrication and the
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The aim of this work is, first, to optimize gas atomization, at the laboratory scale, of the γ -TiAl alloy Ti-45Al-2Nb-2Mn (at.%) + 0.8(vol.%)TiB₂ (Ti4522XD) to maximize the yield of particles with the sizes of interest for LPBF and EBM and, second, to characterize the microstructure of the produced powders. The microstructure of the powders will, finally, be compared with that obtained earlier in the similar alloy systems using larger scale gas atomizers and via other rapid solidification studies.

Experimental procedure

The material under study is a fully lamellar (FL) Ti-45Al-2Nb-2Mn (at.%) + 0.8(vol.%)TiB₂ (Ti4522XD) alloy. The alloy was provided by GfE (Gesellschaft für Elektrometallurgie mbH) and was processed by centrifugal casting at ACCESS e. V. TechCenter (Aachen, Germany). Casting was followed by hot isostatical pressing (HIP) at ~1200 °C and 1700 bar during four hours to improve densification.^[28] Figure 1 illustrates the microstructure of the cast and HIPped alloy, composed of fine lamellae of the α_2 and γ phases, which has been described in detail in the literature.^[29] The reported average colony size is $194 \pm 121 \mu\text{m}$; the average values of the lamellae thickness are $\lambda_{\alpha_2} = 319 \pm 39 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{\gamma} = 287 \pm 133 \text{ nm}$, respectively.^[29] The wide variation of colony sizes resulting from the centrifugal casting process is consistent with previous reports.^[29-32] Further information related to the deformation and fracture mechanisms of this alloy at a wide range of temperatures can be found in earlier works.^[30-32]

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Figure 1. (a) Backscatter electron (BSE) SEM micrograph illustrating the fully lamellar microstructure of the Ti4522XD alloy under investigation following processing by centrifugal casting and hot isostatic pressing; (b) Bright (left) and dark (right) field TEM micrographs illustrating the microstructure at higher magnification. The brighter lamella in the dark field micrograph correspond to the α_2 phase.

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The Ti4522XD alloy was processed by vacuum arc melting gas atomization with high purity Ar (99.999%) in a laboratory scale horizontal Arcast 200 atomizer (Figure 2a), consisting of a cylindrical collector attached to an arc melting furnace furnished with a refrigerated Cu crucible. Before atomization the melting chamber was subjected to several purge cycles and a vacuum level of the order of 10^{-2} torr was stabilized. An arc was then applied between a mobile electrode and a static electrode placed at the Cu crucible, where a block of the Ti4522XD alloy was placed. Once a complete fusion of the intermetallic was achieved, a manual handle was utilized to tilt the crucible and pour down a stream of liquid metal. The Ar gas was then injected through a narrow round slit located at the interior perimeter of a ring shaped nozzle (Figure 2b) at a pressure of about 5.5 MPa.

1 The strong suction effect caused by the ejection of the pressurized gas led to the bending of the
2 downwards trajectory of the liquid metal stream, which was forced to pass through the nozzle and
3 subsequently to break into a large number of fine droplets. The latter transform into fine powder
4 particles as they fly into the powder collector. Optimization of processing parameters (Table 1) such
5 as the arc current and the gas pressure was carried out in order to obtain the highest possible yield
6 of particles with sizes within the ranges that are considered acceptable for additive manufacturing
7 processes such as LPBF ($10 < d < 50 \mu\text{m}$) and EBM ($50 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$).
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36 Figure 2. Laboratory scale atomizer utilized for powder production. (a) Horizontal Arcast 200
37 atomizer; (b) Schematic showing the process of atomization using a round-shaped nozzle.
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41 The composition of the powder particles was analyzed by energy dispersive X-ray
42 spectroscopy (EDX) in a FEI Helios NanoLab 600i field emission gun scanning electron
43 microscope (FEGSEM), which was also utilized to examine the particle morphology. An average of
44 10 measurements were performed for each powder particle size range. The flowability, bulk, and
45 tap density of the powders was measured using a Hall flowmeter. The microstructure of the
46 atomized powder particles was characterized using several complementary techniques. The phases
47 present were analyzed, first, by X-ray diffraction (XRD) in a Panalytical Empyrean X-ray
48 diffractometer furnished with a linear detector. The radiation used was $\text{CuK}\alpha$. Transmission
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1 electron microscopy (TEM) was additionally carried out at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV in a
2 FEI Talos F200X microscope in order to differentiate the α and α_2 phases, which cannot be
3 distinguished by XRD. Convergent beam (CBED) and selected area electron diffraction (SAED)
4 were applied for sample orientation and phase identification. TEM foils were prepared via the
5 trenching-and-lift-out FIB technique. The grain structure and the texture of the powder particles
6 were examined by electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD) in the FEGSEM, which was equipped
7 with an HKL detector, a CCD camera, the Aztec acquisition software, and the Channel 5.0 post-
8 processing analysis package. EBSD examination was conducted at an accelerating voltage of 15-20
9 kV and an electron beam current of 2.7 nA, with a step size ranging between 100 and 200 nm.
10 Measurements were carried out using 4x4 binning with no frame averaging. Sample preparation for
11 EBSD included mechanical mirror-polish with diamond pastes of increasingly finer particle sizes
12 and then a colloidal silica slurry finishing.
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27 The hardness of the powder particles was evaluated using a Hysitron TriboIndenter® TI 950
28 with an environmentally dedicated enclosure where samples were thermally and acoustically
29 isolated. The load was first increased gradually until a maximum value of 10 mN was achieved after
30 15 s, then this load was held constant for 30 s, unloading over the course of another 15 s. Special
31 care was taken to make the indentations at locations away from the particle surfaces in order to
32 avoid spurious effects. For hardness characterization, powder particles were mounted on bakelite
33 resin and then ground using SiC paper with 320, 640, 1200, and 2000 grit sizes, and mechanically
34 polished using 3 μm and 1 μm diamond pastes. Final surface preparation was carried out by chemo-
35 mechanical polishing, using colloidal silica.
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52 **Results and discussion**

53 The range of particle diameters obtained in conventional gas atomizers usually spans from 1
54 μm to 1 mm .^[33] Optimization of gas atomization processes for the production of raw powders for
55 AM powder bed technologies aims, therefore, to increase the yield of fine particles, with diameters
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smaller than 150 μm , as this results in an increased process efficiency and reduced waste. This may be realized by modifying the processing parameters in such a way that the kinetic energy of the metal stream to be atomized becomes larger. To that effect, it is well known that increasing the temperature of the melt and/or the gas pressure and/or the gas flow, or decreasing the metal flow and/or the density of the atomizing gas, may lead to the mentioned goal.^[34]

	Arc current (A)	Gas pressure (MPa)
Atom ₁	450	~5.2
Atom ₂	450	~5.5
Atom ₃	475	~5.5

Table 1. Atomization parameters.

In this work, optimization of gas atomization of the Ti4522XD alloy in a laboratory scale atomizer was carried out. Table 1 summarizes the processing variables corresponding to the three atomization runs included in the present study. Earlier attempts, excluded from this work for the purpose of brevity, allowed to determine an optimum vacuum level in the melting chamber (10^{-2} torr), which is held constant in the three atomization runs shown here. The metal flow, which is manually controlled, is also kept constant within the limits of experimental errors. A final process constraint is the utilization of Ar gas, which is preferred due to its inert nature. The variables that are optimized in the present work are, thus, the gas pressure, and the arc current, which determines the melt temperature. Caution must be exercised when increasing the arc current in order not to trigger evaporation of the elements with lower melting points (such as Al in the TiAl alloy under investigation) when high melt temperatures are achieved. As described in Table 1, atomization run 1 includes an arc current of 450 A and a gas pressure of 5.2 MPa (initial mass=69.5 g). In run 2 the arc current was kept constant at 450 A, while the gas pressure was increased to 5.5 MPa (initial mass=88.5 g). Finally, in run three the arc current was increased to 475 A while the gas kept constant at 5.5 MPa (initial mass=123.8 g). Increasing the arc current beyond this value resulted in significant metal evaporation.

Figure 3. Particle size distribution corresponding to the three atomization processes whose parameter sets are summarized in Table 1. The vertical axis indicates the mass fraction, with respect to the total atomized mass, corresponding to each particle size range. These numbers do not take into account the fact that a residue was always left at the melting crucible and, therefore, the overall efficiency of the process is smaller than what is shown here.

Figure 3 illustrates the particle size distributions corresponding to the three atomization runs under investigation. In run 1, the fraction of particles with $d < 45 \mu\text{m}$ was 3 %, with $45 < d < 100 \mu\text{m}$ was 11 % and with $100 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$ was 13.5 %; in run 2, the fraction of particles with $d < 45 \mu\text{m}$ was 7 %, with $45 < d < 100 \mu\text{m}$ was 20 % and with $100 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$ was 23 %; finally, in run 3, the fraction of particles with $d < 45 \mu\text{m}$ was 9 %, with $45 < d < 100 \mu\text{m}$ was 22 % and with $100 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$ was 21.5 %. Our results show that, indeed, increasing the gas pressure and the arc current led to a substantially larger yield of fine particles. Due to the fact that the Cu melting crucible was refrigerated by water, the presence of a solid alloy residue at its bottom after atomization was unavoidable. The mass fraction of residue varied noticeably for the different atomization runs: in run 1 it amounted to 9 %, in run 2 to 35 %, and in run 3 to 17 %. The apparently erratic variation of the mass fraction of residue between different runs was attributed to the fact that the atomization process under investigation is largely manual in nature.

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Figure 4. SEM micrographs illustrating the morphology of the powder particles (Atom 3) with sizes within the following ranges at two different magnifications: (a) $d < 45 \mu\text{m}$; (b) $45 < d < 100 \mu\text{m}$, and (c) $100 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$.

Particle size	Ti	Al	Mn	Nb
$d < 45 \mu\text{m}$	51.9 ± 1.9	43.5 ± 1.6	2.4 ± 0.4	2.2 ± 0.5
$45 \mu\text{m} < d < 100 \mu\text{m}$	51.9 ± 1.4	44.1 ± 1.2	1.7 ± 0.3	2.2 ± 0.1
$100 \mu\text{m} < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$	53.6 ± 1.4	42.8 ± 1.5	1.3 ± 0.3	2.3 ± 0.2

Table 2. Composition (at.%) of powder particles with diameters belonging to the three ranges of interest: $d < 45 \mu\text{m}$, $45 < d < 100 \mu\text{m}$, and $100 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$. An average of 10 measurements were performed for each size range.

1 Since the atomization run 3 yielded the highest fraction of atomized mass for particles with
2 diameters smaller than 150 μm , these processing conditions were selected. Figure 4 contains three
3 SEM micrographs illustrating the morphology of the powder particles with sizes within the
4 following ranges: $d < 45 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 4a), $45 < d < 100 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 4b), and $100 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$
5 (Figure 4c). It can be clearly seen that, irrespective of size, particles are highly spherical and contain
6 a reduced fraction of satellites, as is desirable for optimum powder spreading in powder bed AM
7 methods. Table 2 summarizes the composition of powder particles as a function of their size. The
8 composition of the particles was found to be homogeneous along the particle diameter, irrespective
9 of particle size. The average Al content is in all cases slightly lower than the nominal composition
10 (45 at.%). This might be indicative of a small degree of evaporation of this element during the
11 melting process. Since AM of this alloy also involves a melting step, further Al evaporation is
12 expected during processing. Printing components of the Ti4522XD alloy by powder based methods
13 would, therefore, require increasing the Al amount in the starting alloy by about 1-2 at. %. The
14 flowability, bulk, and tap density values of 50 g of powders with sizes comprised between 40 and
15 150 μm was measured and the obtained values are, respectively, 29.03 s, 2.47 g/cm^3 , and 2.58
16 g/cm^3 .

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As can be seen in Fig.5, negligible porosity was detected at the particle interiors, even in those with relatively large diameters ($100 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$). The presence of porosity in atomized metallic powders has been addressed in a number of earlier works [35-39], which have utilized SEM image analysis, pycnometry, and synchrotron X-ray tomography as characterization tools. In general, the fraction of pores has been observed to increase with increasing particle diameter, and particularly in particles whose size is larger than $75 \mu\text{m}$, although this depends on the atomization method and on the material under investigation. For example, Chen et al. [35] have found that the porosity volume fraction in a Ti-6Al-4V (at.%) alloy increases from 0.15 % in particles with a size of $50 \mu\text{m}$ to 0.4% in particles with a size of $75 \mu\text{m}$, and to 0.5 % in particles with a size of $150 \mu\text{m}$. Similarly, Gerling et al. [36] atomized a γ -TiAl alloy (Ti-47Al-4(Nb, Mn, Cr, Si) (at.%) by plasma induced gas atomization (PIGA) and observed an increase of the volume fraction of porosity from 0.05 % in particles with a diameter of $40 \mu\text{m}$ to 0.4 % in particles with a size of $150 \mu\text{m}$. Other authors have also qualitatively observed a higher fraction of pores in the largest particles although quantitative measurements are not provided. [38] In most cases, pores at particle interiors are spherical and are thus attributed to Ar gas entrapment.

The fraction of entrapped gas during atomization is related to atomizing parameters such as the melt temperature, the melt flow, and the pressure and purity of the atomizing Ar gas. In general, a higher porosity results from a higher capacity of the gas to “break” the molten metal stream. [40] For example, a higher melt temperature at the point where the gas impinges on the melt stream leads to a higher fraction of entrapped gas because higher temperatures are associated to lower viscosity and surface tension and, therefore, to an increased capacity of the metal liquid to break. Additionally, the fraction of atomizing gas penetrating the melt is inversely related to the melt flow in such a way that, for a fixed gas flow, less relative entrapment is expected when the metal flow increases. Finally, since the density of pure Ar ($\rho_{\text{Ar}} = 1.704 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g/cm}^3$) under ambient conditions is larger than that of air ($\rho_{\text{air}} = 1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g/cm}^3$), the density of the atomizing Ar gas increases with purity. Thus, the velocity that a higher purity Ar gas can achieve, all other parameters being equal,

would be smaller than that reachable in lower purity Ar. Since larger speeds are associated to higher gas entrapment, a higher purity gas would lead to decreased porosity. Related to this, for a fixed gas purity, higher pressures are also linked to a larger degree of gas penetration into the melt..

The presence of a smaller degree of porosity in the present study in comparison with earlier works on TiAl alloys^[36] and other metals^[35,37-38] must be attributed to the use of different atomization set-up and conditions. Indeed, in the present study a laboratory scale horizontal vacuum arc melting atomizer is utilized (Fig. 2), while earlier works were carried out using either plasma induced gas atomization (PIGA)^[36] or vertical vacuum induced induction melting gas atomizersm (VIGA)^[35,37-38]. It must be noted here that the conditions that favor gas entrapment (higher porosity) also lead to a higher fraction of smaller particles during atomization. In the study by Gerling et al.^[36] the fraction of particles with $d < 150 \mu\text{m}$ is 90%, and in the work of Chen et al.^[35] it amounts to 72%. In both cases, the yield of small particles is, indeed, significantly higher than that achieved in the present study (a máximum of 58 % in Atom 3).

Figure 6. Phase analysis. (a) X-ray diffractogram illustrating the main peaks corresponding to powder particles in three size ranges: $d < 45 \mu\text{m}$, $45 < d < 100 \mu\text{m}$, and $100 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$; (b) selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern corresponding to a particle with a diameter of $100 \mu\text{m}$.

1 The microstructure of the powder particles was characterized using a range of
2 complementary techniques. X-ray diffraction was utilized initially for phase characterization. This
3 technique revealed that, irrespective of particle size, the high cooling rate employed resulted in the
4 stabilization of a single α/α_2 phase due to the inhibition of γ nucleation. Figure 6a compares sections
5 of the X-ray diffractograms corresponding to Debye (2θ) angles comprised between 37° and 44° ,
6 where two α/α_2 peaks, (0001) and (20-21), can be observed. Since XRD does not allow to
7 distinguish between the α and the α_2 phases, in order to determine the precise nature of the
8 stabilized single phase, a TEM foil with a $\langle 1\bar{1}00 \rangle_{\alpha_2}$ zone axis was extracted from representative
9 particles corresponding to each size range. As an example, Figure 6b illustrates the selected area
10 electron diffraction diagram (SAED) corresponding to a particle with a diameter of 100 μm . The
11 differences in the intensities corresponding to $11\bar{2}0_{\alpha_2}$ and $22\bar{4}0_{\alpha_2}$ reflections are consistent with the
12 long range ordering of Ti and Al atoms in the $D0_{19}$ structure, thus confirming the presence of the α_2
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31 In γ -TiAl alloys, the colony size, the volume fraction of α_2 and γ phases, the lamellae width
32 (λ), as well as the distance between domain boundaries, depend on the specific heat-treatment
33 temperature and cooling rate from the α phase field.^[41] In particular, it is known that cooling rates
34 below about 10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{s}$ favor the formation of lamellar microstructures whereas those above 100 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{s}$
35 promote the stabilization of the single α or α_2 phases at room temperature due to the inhibition of γ
36 nucleation.^[42-43] During atomization, cooling rates of the order of 10^4 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{s}$ to 10^5 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{s}$ are achieved,
37 and thus this is consistent with the observed stabilization of the α_2 phase.
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49 Powder particles were observed to be formed by equiaxed grains bounded by wavy grain
50 boundaries, as is typical of rapidly solidified polycrystals in which boundary straightening is
51 prevented by the sluggish diffusion rate.^[44] Figure 7 depicts the microtexture of a particle with a
52 diameter of 120 μm . In particular, the EBSD inverse pole figure map depicting the orientation of
53 the normal direction and the (0001), (11-20), and (10-10) direct pole figures are shown. The
54 average grain size, measured by the linear intercept method, is approximately 10 μm . The
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corresponding texture is rather weak, as expected in a solidification structure.^[45] Figure 9 illustrates the EBSD inverse pole figure map corresponding to a particle with a diameter of 20 μm , which possesses a grain size of 5.8 μm and an equally weak texture. Hardness was measured by nanoindentation in particles with sizes comprised between 45 and 100 μm , and between 100 and 150 μm . The values obtained were, respectively, 5.8 ± 0.7 GPa, and 7.8 ± 0.5 GPa. Reliable measurements could not be performed in the powder particles with diameters smaller than 45 μm , where the effect of the particle-resin interfaces contributed to increase dramatically the scatter in the measurements.

Figure 7. (a) EBSD inverse pole figure map depicting the orientation of the normal direction in a powder particle with a diameter of 120 μm ; (b) direct pole figures illustrating the corresponding texture. The X_0 and Y_0 directions correspond, respectively, to the horizontal and vertical directions in Figure 6a.

Figure 8. EBSD inverse pole figure map depicting the orientation of the normal direction in a powder particle with a diameter of $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$.

In the following, the phase distribution obtained in the atomized Ti4522XD powders of the current work is compared to those of similar TiAl alloys processed using various atomization methods. In agreement with the findings presented above, gas atomization studies on γ -TiAl alloys report an increasing volume fraction of the α_2 phase in the finest particles, which solidify at the highest cooling rates^[46-49]. However, the volume fraction of this phase for a specific particle diameter is highly dependent on alloy composition as well as on the atomization method. For example, Huang et al.^[46] have recently processed a Ti-46.15Al-2.1Nb-1.7 Cr-(B,Si,Y) (at.%) by Ar mediated gas atomization and report the presence of a single α_2 phase in particles with diameters smaller than $100 \mu\text{m}$ and a combination of α_2 and γ phases in larger particles. Yang et al.^[47] prepared Ti-48Al (at.%) powder by high pressure gas atomization in an Ar spray chamber environment, where the TiAl alloy was melted by levitation, and observed a size dependent phase structure. The finest particles, with diameters smaller than $15 \mu\text{m}$, were formed by cellular (α_2 phase, 1-3 μm cell size, 80% volume fraction) and lamellar structures ($\alpha_2 + \gamma$ phases, 20% volume fraction). They demonstrated that the volume fraction of γ phase could be increased up to 85% in particles larger than $120 \mu\text{m}$. Guyon et al.^[48] gas atomized a Ti-47.3 Al-2.0 Nb-1.9 Cr (at.%) in a neutral environment, and obtained a highly metastable microstructure formed mainly by the α phase (95 wt.%), the γ phase (5 wt.%), and traces of the the β /B2 phase. Finally, Muñoz-Moreno et al.^[49] processed the Ti4522XD alloy by electron induction melting gas atomization (EIGA) and reported

1 the presence of the α phase in particles with diameters smaller than 50 μm . The absence of the α_2
2 phase, which is observed in the present study in particles of similar size, is consistent with the
3 higher cooling rates associated with EIGA vs. VIGA [50].
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6 The powder microstructures obtained in the present study are similar to those reported by
7 Palomares-García et al.^[29], who utilized a Gleeble 3800 thermomechanical simulator to carry out
8 rapid quenching of the Ti4522XD alloy. In their work, the cast and HIPped alloy was subsequently
9 heated at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$ up to a temperature of 1390 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, kept at that temperature during 20 s, and finally
10 water quenched at a measured cooling rate of 2000 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$. They observed the retention of a single
11 supersaturated α_2 phase, with an average grain size of $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$, and a hardness value of 6.8 ± 0.4
12 GPa. The similarity between these values and those reported here suggests that Gleeble technology
13 might be suitable to simulate gas atomized microstructures in fine particles of γ -TiAl alloys and
14 thus might constitute a very useful tool for materials exploration for AM.
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31 **Conclusions**

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33 The aim of this work was, first, to find optimum processing parameters in a laboratory scale
34 gas atomizer for the production of Ti4522XD powders with sizes that meet the requirements of
35 powder bed AM methods ($d < 150 \mu\text{m}$) and, second, to characterize the resulting powders using
36 several complementary techniques. The following conclusions were obtained from the present
37 study:
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- 45 1. The yield of particles with sizes smaller than 150 μm was significantly improved
46 by increasing the Ar gas pressure and the arc current. Optimum gas atomization
47 conditions included a chamber vacuum of 10^{-2} torr, a gas pressure of 5.5 MPa,
48 and an arc current of 475 A. Under these conditions, the mass fractions of
49 particles (with respect to the total atomized mass) with sizes comprised within the
50 three intervals of interest ($d < 45 \mu\text{m}$, $45 < d < 100 \mu\text{m}$, and $100 < d < 150 \mu\text{m}$.)
51 were, respectively, 9, 22, and 21.5 %.
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2. The composition of the atomized powders varies with respect of that of the initial material. In particular, the Al content in the powders was found to be slightly below (1-2 at.%) the nominal composition.
 3. Particles with diameters smaller than 150 μm are spherical in shape and have a small fraction of satellites and negligible porosity.
 4. Powder particles with diameters smaller than 150 μm are single α_2 polycrystals. The average grain size increases with increasing particle size, from ~ 6 μm in particles with diameters smaller than 45 μm , to ~ 10 μm in particles with diameters larger than 100 μm .
 5. The gas atomized powders with sizes smaller than 150 μm meet the morphological requirements (sphericity, absence of satellites, reduced porosity) of AM powder based methods. Obtaining a printed part with a Ti4522XD composition of would, however, require increasing the Al content in the raw alloys by about 2-4 % in the initial material (pre-atomization).

Acknowledgments

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AM acknowledges funding from the Spanish Ministry of Employment and Social Security (Youth employment plan). The research leading to these results has received funding from the Madrid region under programme S2018/NMT-4381-MAT4.0-CM and from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness through project MAT2016-77189-R. We are grateful for the kind assistance of Alberto Palomares and Miguel Castillo (TEM measurements), R. Muñoz-Moreno (SEM characterization), M. Monclús (nanoindentation), and Marcos Angulo (gas atomization).

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